

1 **LUZP1, a novel regulator of primary cilia and the actin cytoskeleton, is a**
2 **contributing factor in Townes-Brocks Syndrome**

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39 **ABSTRACT**

40

41 Primary cilia are sensory organelles crucial for cell signaling during
42 development and organ homeostasis. Cilia arise from centrosomes and their formation
43 and function is governed by numerous factors. Through our studies on Townes-
44 Brocks Syndrome (TBS), a rare disease linked to abnormal cilia formation in human
45 fibroblasts, we uncovered the leucine-zipper protein LUZP1 as an interactor of
46 truncated SALL1, a dominantly-acting protein causing the disease. Using TurboID
47 proximity labeling and pulldowns, we show that LUZP1 associates with factors linked
48 to centrosome and actin filaments. Here, we show that LUZP1 is a cilia regulator. It
49 localizes around the centrioles and to actin cytoskeleton. Loss of LUZP1 reduces F-
50 actin levels, facilitates ciliogenesis and alters Sonic Hedgehog signaling, pointing to a
51 key role in cytoskeleton-cilia interdependency. Truncated SALL1 increases the
52 ubiquitin proteasome-mediated degradation of LUZP1. Together with other factors,
53 alterations in LUZP1 may be contributing to TBS etiology.

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57 **Keywords:** LUZP1, actin cytoskeleton, SALL1, primary cilia, rare disease, Townes-
58 Brocks Syndrome

59

60 **Abbreviations:** TBS, Townes Brocks Syndrome

61 INTRODUCTION

62 Townes-Brocks Syndrome (TBS1 [MIM: 107480]) is an autosomal dominant
63 genetic disease, caused by mutations in a transcription factor called SALL1,
64 characterized by the presence of imperforate anus, dysplastic ears, thumb
65 malformations and often renal and heart impairment, among other symptoms
66 (Botzenhart et al., 2007; Kohlhase et al., 1998). Some of these features overlap those
67 in the ciliopathic spectrum. It has been recently demonstrated that primary cilia
68 defects are contributing factors to TBS etiology (Bozal-Basterra et al., 2018).
69 Truncated SALL1, either by itself or in complex with full length protein (SALL1^{FL}),
70 can interact with CCP110 and CEP97. As a consequence, those negative regulators
71 are reduced at the mother centriole (MC) and ciliogenesis is promoted (Bozal-
72 Basterra et al., 2018).

73 Primary cilia are sensory organelles that have a crucial role in cell signaling
74 and protein trafficking during development and organ homeostasis. Although several
75 key pathways are influenced by cilia function (Wnt, TGFbeta, PDGFRalpha, Notch),
76 the best characterized is the Sonic Hedgehog (Shh) pathway (Goetz & Anderson,
77 2010). Briefly, Shh binds to its receptor PTCH1 and leads to ciliary enrichment of the
78 transmembrane protein Smoothed (SMO), with concomitant conversion of the
79 transcription factor GLI3 from a cleaved repressor to a full-length activator form,
80 leading to activation of Shh target genes. Two such genes are *PTCH1* and *GLII*
81 (encoding the Shh receptor and a transcriptional activator, respectively), exemplifying
82 the feedback and fine-tuning of the Shh pathway.

83 Cilia arise from the centrosome, a cellular organelle composed of two barrel-
84 shaped microtubule-based structures called the centrioles. Primary cilia formation is
85 very dynamic throughout the cell cycle. Cilia are nucleated from the MC at the

86 membrane-anchored basal body upon entry into the G0 phase, and they reabsorb as
87 cells progress from G1 to S phase, completely disassembling in mitosis (Rezabkova et
88 al., 2016). Centrioles are surrounded by protein-based matrix, the pericentriolar
89 material (PCM) (Conduit et al., 2015; Vertii et al., 2016). In eukaryotic cells, PCM
90 proteins are concentrically arranged around a centriole in a highly organized manner
91 (Fu & Glover, 2012; Lawo et al., 2012; Mennella et al., 2012; Sonnen et al., 2012).
92 Based on this observation, proper positioning and organization of PCM proteins may
93 be important for promoting different cellular processes in a spatially regulated way (T.
94 S. Kim et al., 2019). Not surprisingly, aberrations in the function of PCM scaffolds
95 are associated with several human diseases, including cancer and ciliopathies (Gonczy,
96 2015; Nigg & Holland, 2018). Cilia assembly is regulated by diverse factors. Among
97 them, CCP110 and CEP97 form a cilia suppressor complex that, when removed from
98 the MC, allows ciliogenesis to proceed (Spektor et al., 2007). The actin cytoskeleton
99 is also emerging as key regulator of cilia formation and function, with both negative
100 and positive roles (Copeland, 2019).

101 Ciliary dysfunction often results in early developmental problems including
102 hydrocephalus, neural tube closure defects (NTD) and left-right anomalies (Fliegauf
103 et al., 2007). These features are often reported in a variety of diseases, collectively
104 known as ciliopathies, caused by failure of cilia formation and/or cilia-dependent
105 signaling (Hildebrandt et al., 2011). In the adult, depending on the underlying
106 mutation, ciliopathies present a broad spectrum of phenotypes comprising cystic
107 kidneys, polydactyly, obesity or heart malformation.

108 Truncated SALL1 likely interferes with multiple factors to give rise to TBS
109 phenotypes. Here we focus on LUZP1, a leucine-zipper motif containing protein that
110 was identified by proximity proteomics as an interactor of truncated SALL1 (Bozal-

111 Basterra et al., 2018). LUZP1 has been previously identified as an interactor of
112 ACTR2 (ARP2 actin related protein 2 homologue) and filamin A (FLNA) and,
113 recently, as an actin cross-linking protein (Hein et al., 2015; Wang & Nakamura,
114 2019). Furthermore, LUZP1 shows homology to FILIP1, a protein interactor of
115 FLNA and actin (Gad et al., 2012; Nagano et al., 2004). Interestingly, mutations in
116 *Luzp1* resulted in cardiovascular defects and cranial NTD in mice (Hsu et al., 2008),
117 phenotypes within the spectrum of those seen in TBS individuals and mouse models
118 of dysfunctional cilia (Botzenhart et al., 2007; Botzenhart et al., 2005; N. Klena et al.,
119 2016; Kohlhase et al., 1998; Surka et al., 2001; Toomer et al., 2019). Both the non-
120 canonical Wnt/PCP (Wingless-Integrated/planar cell polarity) and the Shh pathways
121 are influenced by the presence of functional cilia and regulate neural tube closure and
122 patterning (Campbell, 2003; Copp, 2005; Fuccillo et al., 2006). Remarkably, ectopic
123 Shh was observed in the dorsal lateral neuroepithelium of the *Luzp1*^{-/-} mice (Hsu et al.,
124 2008). However, in spite of the phenotypic overlaps, a link between LUZP1 and
125 ciliogenesis has not been explored.

126 Here we demonstrate that LUZP1 is associated with centrosomal and actin
127 cytoskeleton-related proteins. We show that LUZP1 localizes to the PCM, actin
128 cytoskeleton and the midbody, and also provide evidence towards its regulatory role
129 on actin dynamics and its subsequent impact on ciliogenesis. Notably, we demonstrate
130 that *Luzp1*^{-/-} cells exhibit reduced filamentous actin (F-actin), longer primary cilia,
131 higher rates of ciliogenesis and increased Shh signaling. Furthermore, TBS-derived
132 primary fibroblasts show a reduction in LUZP1 and actin filaments, possibly through
133 SALL1-regulated LUZP1 degradation via the ubiquitin (Ub)-proteasome system
134 (UPS). As a novel regulator of ciliogenesis and the actin cytoskeleton, LUZP1 might
135 contribute to the aberrant cilia phenotype in TBS.

136

137 **RESULTS**

138

139 **SALL1 interacts with LUZP1**

140 Using proximity proteomics, we have previously shown that a truncated and
141 mislocalized form of SALL1 present in TBS individuals (SALL1²⁷⁵) can interact
142 aberrantly with cytoplasmic proteins (Bozal-Basterra et al., 2018). LUZP1 was found
143 among the most enriched proteins in the SALL1²⁷⁵ proximal interactome. We
144 confirmed this finding by independent BioID experiments analyzed by Western blot
145 using a LUZP1-specific antibody (Figure 1A and Figure 1-figure supplement 1). To
146 further characterize the interaction of LUZP1 with truncated SALL1, we performed
147 pulldowns using tagged SALL1²⁷⁵-YFP in HEK 293FT cells. Our results showed that
148 endogenous LUZP1 was able to interact with SALL1²⁷⁵, confirming our proximity
149 proteomics data (Figure 1-figure supplement 2A, lane 6, and Figure 1-figure
150 supplement 1). The interaction with SALL1²⁷⁵ persisted in presence of overexpressed
151 SALL1^{FL} (Figure 1-figure supplement 2A, lane 9, and Figure 1-figure supplement 1),
152 suggesting that heterodimerization of the truncated and FL forms does not inhibit the
153 interaction with LUZP1. When expressed alone, we noted that SALL1^{FL}-YFP also
154 interacts with LUZP1 in pulldown assays (Figure 1-figure supplement 2A and Figure
155 1-figure supplement 1). As these proteins have distinct localizations (nuclear and
156 cytoplasmic, respectively), the interaction likely occurs in post-lysis cell extracts
157 (more in Discussion). These results show that the truncated form of SALL1 expressed
158 in TBS individuals, either by itself or in complex with the FL form, can interact with
159 LUZP1.

160

161 **LUZP1 interacts with centrosomal and actin cytoskeleton components**

162 To gain insights into the function of LUZP1, we sought to identify its
163 proximal interactome using the TurboID approach (Branon et al., 2018). We used
164 RPE1 cells stably expressing low levels of FLAG-TurboID-LUZP1 (TbID-LUZP1) or
165 FLAG-TurboID (TbID) as control. Transduced cells showed sub-endogenous
166 expression levels of TbID-LUZP1 (Figure 1-figure supplement 2B, two asterisks;
167 endogenous, two open arrowheads). Staining of transfected cells revealed that,
168 proteins biotinylated by TbID are diffusely localized throughout the nucleus and
169 cytoplasm, whereas those biotinylated by TbID-LUZP1 are localized primarily at the
170 centrosome and actin cytoskeleton, as shown by fluorescent streptavidin (Figure 1-
171 figure supplement 2C). Total lysates from TbID-LUZP1 or TbID-expressing cells
172 were subjected to streptavidin pulldown and isolated proteins were analyzed by liquid
173 chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS). 234 high-confidence
174 proximity LUZP1 interactors were enriched in the TbID-LUZP1 *vs* the TbID
175 proteome in three replicates (Source Data 1). Proteins enriched among the identified
176 LUZP1 proximal interactors were centrosomal and actin cytoskeleton-related proteins
177 (Figure 1B-C). With the purpose of obtaining a functional overview of the main
178 pathways associated to LUZP1, a comparative Gene Ontology (GO) analysis was
179 performed with all the hits enriched in TbID-LUZP1 *versus* TbID cells. In the
180 Cellular Component domain, “actin cytoskeleton”, “microtubule cytoskeleton”,
181 “centrosome”, “cilium” and “midbody” terms were highlighted among others (Figure
182 1D and Source Data 1). In the category of Biological Process, LUZP1 proteome
183 showed enrichment in the "microtubule cytoskeleton organization", “cell division”,
184 “cilium assembly”, “vesicle-mediated transport”, “microtubule organizing center
185 organization” and “cell adhesion” categories among others (Figure 1D and Source

186 Data 1). With respect to Molecular Function, LUZP1 also showed enrichment in
187 cytoskeleton-related proteins ("actin binding", "actinin binding" and "microtubule
188 binding" terms; Figure 1D and Source Data 1). 37 or 96 of the verified or potential,
189 respectively, centrosome/cilia gene products previously identified by proteomic
190 studies (Alves-Cruzeiro et al., 2014; Gupta et al., 2015) were found as LUZP1
191 proximal interactors, supporting the enrichment of centrosome-related proteins among
192 the potential interactors of LUZP1. In addition, 45 of LUZP1 proximal interactors
193 were present among the actin-localized proteins identified by the Human Protein
194 Atlas project based on subcellular localization to actin filaments (Uhlen et al., 2015).

195

196 **LUZP1 localizes to the centrosome, actin cytoskeleton and midbody**

197 We examined the subcellular localization of LUZP1 in diverse cell types. First,
198 immunostainings showed that endogenous LUZP1 surrounds both centrioles, labelled
199 by centrin-2 (CETN2) in human RPE1 cells (Figure 2A) and gamma-tubulin in
200 human dermal fibroblasts (Figure 2-video 1) (for specificity of LUZP1 antibody,
201 check Figure 5). We examined LUZP1 localization at the centrosome in synchronized
202 RPE1 cells. LUZP1 was reduced at the centrosome during G2/M and G0 phases
203 (Figure 2-figure supplement 1). Interestingly, LUZP1 levels increased upon treatment
204 with the proteasome inhibitor MG132 in G0 phase arrested-RPE1 cells. All together,
205 these results indicate that LUZP1 levels are reduced at the centrosome in G2/M phase
206 and upon starvation, and this reduction might be mediated by the UPS. The
207 localization of LUZP1 at the centrosome was reproduced in U2OS cells expressing
208 *LUZP1-YFP* (Fig. 2B-D). We did not observe colocalization of LUZP1 with the distal
209 centriolar marker CCP110 (Figure 2B), indicating that LUZP1 is likely found at the
210 proximal end of both centrioles. We further imaged LUZP1 along with pericentrin

211 (PCNT) and PCM1, markers of PCM. Interestingly, we observed that LUZP1
212 enveloped PCNT (Figure 2C), with LUZP1 itself being surrounded by PCM1 (Figure
213 2D). These results suggest that LUZP1 might be a novel PCM associated-protein,
214 decorating the proximal end of both centrioles. In concordance with this localization,
215 LUZP1 was associated to PCM1 in TurboID experiments (Source Data 1).

216 In addition to the localization at the centrosome/basal body, LUZP1 also localized to
217 actin stress fibers (Figure 2E) and to the midbody (Figure 2F) in U2OS cells.

218

219 **LUZP1 shows reduction at the centrosome in TBS fibroblasts and interacts with** 220 **centrosome-associated proteins**

221

222 Based on the LUZP1 interaction with truncated SALL1, we checked its
223 subcellular localization in fibroblasts derived from a TBS individual (TBS²⁷⁵; see
224 Materials and Methods) as well as non-TBS control. We observed that LUZP1 was
225 markedly decreased at the centrosome of TBS²⁷⁵ cells compared to control cells in
226 non-starved conditions (Figure 3A-C). Furthermore, LUZP1 levels decreased in
227 starved vs non-starved control cells (Figure 3A-C), while centrosomal size remained
228 unaltered (Figure 3C, right panel). We previously found that SALL1²⁷⁵-YFP
229 interacted with the centrosome-associated ciliogenesis suppressors, CCP110 and
230 CEP97 (Bozal-Basterra et al., 2018), so we checked whether LUZP1 could also
231 interact with these factors. Indeed, LUZP1-YFP interacts with CCP110 and CEP97 in
232 both WT (293^{WT}) and TBS model (293³³⁵) HEK 293FT cells (Figure 3D, lanes 5 and
233 7, respectively and Figure 3-figure supplement 1) (Bozal-Basterra et al., 2018). Less
234 CCP110 and CEP97 was recovered in LUZP1-YFP pulldowns from 293³³⁵ cells, but
235 this is likely due to the reduced LUZP1-YFP seen in those cells (Figure 3D, Input,

236 lanes 1 and 2 *vs* lane 3 and 4 and Figure 3-figure supplement 1). Beyond pulldowns,
237 we found that immunoprecipitation of endogenous LUZP1 led to co-purification of
238 endogenous CCP110 (Figure 3E and Figure 3-figure supplement 1) and that anti-
239 CEP97 antibodies immunoprecipitated endogenous LUZP1 (Figure 3F and Figure 3-
240 figure supplement 1). Both CCP110 and CEP97 were also identified as proximal
241 interactors of TbID-LUZP1 (Source Data 1). Immunofluorescent colocalization on
242 centrioles of LUZP1 (proximal) and CCP110 (distal) was not evident, suggesting that
243 the interaction is indirect or occurs before proteins reach their destinations. However,
244 these key regulators of ciliogenesis are just two of multiple centrosomal proteins
245 associated with LUZP1, suggesting that LUZP1 may have a function at this dynamic
246 organelle.

247

248 **LUZP1 localizes to actin and is altered in TBS fibroblasts**

249 In addition to the centrosome/basal body, LUZP1 also localized to actin stress
250 fibers, as well as the midbody in dividing cells (Figure 2). Intriguingly, when LUZP1
251 levels were examined in TBS²⁷⁵ cells, a reduction in both actin-associated LUZP1 and
252 phalloidin-labelled stress fibers was observed when compared to control cells
253 (Figures 4A-C). These results indicate that actin cytoskeleton might be altered in TBS
254 cells. Using pulldown assays, we confirmed that LUZP1-YFP interacts with both
255 actin and FLNA (Figure 4D and Figure 4-figure supplement 1). Notably, actin, FLNA,
256 alpha-actinin, palladin, LIMA1/Eplin and other stress fiber-associated proteins are
257 proximal interactors of TbID-LUZP1 (Source Data 1). To examine whether LUZP1
258 levels change upon F-actin perturbation, HEK 293FT cells were treated with
259 Cytochalasin D (CytoD), an inhibitor of actin polymerization. No changes in LUZP1
260 levels upon actin depolymerization were observed when cells were lysed in strong

261 lysis conditions (WB5) (Figure 4E-F and Figure 4-figure supplement 1). However, we
262 observed increased LUZP1 levels using mild lysis conditions (0.1% Triton X-100;
263 Figure 4E-F and Figure 4-figure supplement 1). These results reflect that the integrity
264 of the actin cytoskeleton may influence the solubility but not the stability of LUZP1.

265

266 **LUZP1 plays a role in primary cilia formation and Shh signaling**

267 Based on the localization of LUZP1 at the centrosome, its interaction with
268 centrosomal proteins and the defects in ciliogenesis previously observed in TBS cells
269 (Bozal-Basterra et al., 2018), we hypothesized that LUZP1 might have a role in cilia
270 formation. To examine this, we analyzed ciliogenesis in Shh-LIGHT2 cells, a cell line
271 derived from immortalized mouse NIH3T3 fibroblasts that can display primary cilia
272 and report on Shh pathway status using integrated luciferase reporters (herein
273 designated as WT) (Taipale et al., 2000). Using CRISPR/Cas9 gene editing directed
274 to exon 1 of murine *Luzp1*, we generated Shh-LIGHT2 mouse embryonic fibroblasts
275 null for *Luzp1* (*Luzp1*^{-/-} cells). For genetic rescue experiments, LUZP1 was restored
276 to these cells by the expression of human *LUZP1-YFP* fusion (+LUZP1 cells). To
277 examine the effect of the *Luzp1* mutation and rescue strategies, we used anti-LUZP1
278 antibody and checked LUZP1 localization associated with the actin cytoskeleton and
279 the centrosome by immunofluorescence (Figure 5A,B), and its levels of expression by
280 Western blot (Figure 5C and Figure 5-figure supplement 1) in WT, *Luzp1*^{-/-} and
281 +LUZP1 cells. These experiments showed the effectiveness of the knockout and
282 rescue strategies.

283 To analyze the role of LUZP1 in ciliation, WT, *Luzp1*^{-/-} and +LUZP1 cells
284 were plated at equal densities and induced to ciliate for 48 hours by serum withdrawal
285 (starved; Figure 6A). We quantified ciliation rates and primary cilia length in non-

286 starved and starved cells. *Luzp1*^{-/-} fibroblasts displayed higher ciliation rate (60%)
287 than WT (10.5%) and +LUZP1 (22.2%) when the cells were not subjected to
288 starvation (Figure 6B). However, *Luzp1*^{-/-} cells were not significantly more ciliated
289 than WT or +LUZP1 fibroblasts upon 48 hours of starvation (Figure 6B). In addition,
290 primary cilia in *Luzp1*^{-/-} cells were significantly longer than in non-starved WT
291 cycling cells (Figure 6A and C), while under starvation the differences were not
292 significant (Figure 6A and C). Note that, differently than the ciliation rate, cilia length
293 was not rescued by adding human LUZP1. Taken together, these results confirm that
294 *Luzp1*^{-/-} cells display longer and more abundant primary cilia compared to WT cells
295 in cycling conditions and indicate that LUZP1 might affect primary cilia dynamics.

296 One key event in ciliogenesis is the depletion of CCP110 and its partner
297 CEP97 from the distal end of the MC, promoting the ciliary activating program in
298 somatic cells (Goetz et al., 2012; Kleylein-Sohn et al., 2007; Prosser & Morrison,
299 2015; Spektor et al., 2007; Tsang et al., 2008). We analyzed the centrosomal
300 localization of CCP110 in WT and *Luzp1*^{-/-} cells by immunofluorescence. Consistent
301 with the higher ciliogenesis rate, CCP110 was present at two centrosomal spots at a
302 lower proportion in *Luzp1*^{-/-} cells (19%) compared to WT (84%; Figure 6D and E).
303 This result suggests that the lack of LUZP1 might result in CCP110 reduction at the
304 centrosome, leading to higher frequency of ciliogenesis in *Luzp1*^{-/-} cells, and is
305 reminiscent to the results obtained in TBS cells (Bozal-Basterra et al., 2018).

306 It is well-established that mammalian Shh signal transduction is dependent on
307 functional primary cilia (Huangfu et al., 2003; Yin et al., 2009). Therefore, we
308 examined whether Shh signaling is altered in *Luzp1*^{-/-} cells. Cells were starved for 24
309 hours and incubated in the presence or absence of purmorphamine (a SMO agonist)
310 for 24 hours to activate the Shh pathway. The mRNA expression of two Shh target

311 genes (*Gli1* and *Ptch1*) was quantified by qRT-PCR (Figure 7A,B). We found that
312 *Gli1* and *Ptch1* expression levels in non-treated *Luzp1*^{-/-} cells were higher than in WT
313 cells (*Gli1* 1.5 fold and *Ptch1* 2.3 fold increase in *Luzp1*^{-/-} vs WT cells without
314 purmorphamine) (Figure 7A,B). To further study the role of LUZP1 in Shh signaling,
315 we analyzed GLI3 processing by Western blot using total lysates extracted from WT
316 vs *Luzp1*^{-/-} cells. Without purmorphamine induction, we found a significantly higher
317 ratio of GLI3 activating form vs GLI3 repressive form (GLI3-A:GLI3-R) in *Luzp1*^{-/-}
318 cells compared to WT (2.9 fold increase in *Luzp1*^{-/-} cells vs WT) (Figure 7C and
319 Figure 7-figure supplement 2). After induction, the values were similar for *Luzp1*^{-/-}
320 and WT cells. We also examined the effects of lacking *Luzp1* on Shh signaling by
321 measuring the activity of the Shh-responsive Firefly luciferase reporter in the
322 presence or absence of purmorphamine for 24 hours to activate the Shh pathway
323 (Figure 7D,E). Consistent with the *Gli1* and *Ptch1* qRT-PCR data, non-treated *Luzp1*^{-/-}
324 ^{-/-} cells showed higher Shh activity compared to control or +LUZP1 cells, as observed
325 in TBS-derived cells (Figure 7D). However, the induction capacity of *Luzp1*^{-/-} cells
326 upon purmorphamine treatment was reduced compared to WT or +LUZP1 cells
327 (Figure 7E). Altogether, the observed defects in *Ptch1* and *Gli1* gene expression and
328 Shh reporter misregulation point to a role for LUZP1 in Shh signaling.

329

330 **LUZP1 and F-actin levels are correlated**

331 Based on the localization of LUZP1 to actin stress fibers and interaction with
332 cytoskeletal proteins, we hypothesized that LUZP1 might also affect F-actin
333 cytoskeleton. We observed a reduction in F-actin (labelled by phalloidin) in the
334 *Luzp1*^{-/-} cells compared to WT, which was recovered in +LUZP1 cells (Figure 8A).
335 We also note the correlation between LUZP1 levels and actin filaments in non-starved

336 versus starved WT fibroblasts (Figure 8B,C). These results suggest that LUZP1 can
337 stabilize actin stress fibers and that starvation triggers both LUZP1 and F-actin
338 reduction.

339

340 **Truncated SALL1 promotes LUZP1 degradation via the ubiquitin proteasome** 341 **system**

342 In concordance with immunofluorescence results in Figures 3 and 4, we
343 confirmed a reduction in total LUZP1 levels in TBS²⁷⁵ cells compared to controls by
344 Western blot (Figure 9A,B and Figure 9-figure supplement 1). No transcriptional
345 changes in *LUZP1* expression were detected between control and TBS²⁷⁵ samples
346 (Figure 9-figure supplement 2), so we hypothesized that truncated SALL1 might lead
347 to UPS-mediated LUZP1 degradation. We analyzed LUZP1 levels after treatment
348 with the proteasome inhibitor MG132, both in control and TBS²⁷⁵ cells, and LUZP1
349 levels were increased to a higher extent in TBS²⁷⁵ compared to control cells (1.8 fold
350 increase in control vs 2.4 fold increase in TBS²⁷⁵ cells) (Figure 9A,B). Moreover, we
351 confirmed the reduction of LUZP1 levels in the CRISPR/Cas9 TBS model cell line
352 (293³³⁵), compared to its parental cell line (293^{WT}) (Figure 9C,D and Figure 9-figure
353 supplement 1), and likewise in HEK 293FT cells stably overexpressing truncated
354 SALL1 (*SALL1*²⁷⁵-*YFP*) compared to cells with *YFP* as control (Figure 9E,F and
355 Figure 9-figure supplement 1). A more prominent increase in LUZP1 accumulation
356 upon MG132 treatment was also observed in 293³³⁵ and HEK 293FT cells
357 overexpressing *SALL1*²⁷⁵-*YFP* compared to controls (Figure 9C,D and Figure 9E,F,
358 respectively, and Figure 9-figure supplement 1). Additionally, we also observed
359 LUZP1 accumulation upon MG132 treatment by immunofluorescence in RPE1 cells,
360 both at the actin cytoskeleton (Figure 9G, upper panels) and at the centrosome (Figure

361 9G, lower panels). All together, these results show that LUZP1 levels are sensitive to
362 degradation via the UPS pathway and suggest that truncated SALL1 may contribute
363 to this process. Furthermore, we compared LUZP1 ubiquitination in 293^{WT} vs 293³³⁵
364 cells using the BioUb strategy (see Materials and Methods) (Pirone et al., 2017). In
365 the pulldowns, we could observe a prominent band in presence of BioUb, possibly
366 corresponding to a monoubiquitinated form of LUZP1 (Figure 9H and Figure 9-figure
367 supplement 1). This form was present in 293^{WT} and 293³³⁵ cells, and increased in the
368 presence of MG132 in both cell lines. In addition, we observed a smear at higher
369 molecular weight corresponding to polyubiquitinated forms of LUZP1 (Figure 9H,
370 Biotin PD and Figure 9-figure supplement 1). Notably, the LUZP1 ubiquitinated pool
371 relative to the input levels was higher in 293³³⁵ compared to 293^{WT} cells upon MG132
372 treatment (Figure 9H, Biotin PD, lane 8 vs lane 11 and Figure 9-figure supplement 1).
373 These results suggest that truncated SALL1 promotes LUZP1 degradation through the
374 UPS pathway.

375

376 **LUZP1 overexpression represses cilia formation and increases F-actin levels in** 377 **TBS fibroblasts**

378 Our results suggest that LUZP1 could be a mediator of TBS cilia phenotype and
379 that this could be caused, at least in part, by the increased degradation of LUZP1
380 triggered by truncated SALL1. Therefore, increasing LUZP1 levels in TBS cells
381 might affect the cilia and actin cytoskeleton phenotypes. To check whether an
382 increase in LUZP1 levels is sufficient to repress ciliogenesis in primary human
383 fibroblasts, Control and TBS²⁷⁵ cells were transduced with *YFP* or *LUZP1-YFP* using
384 lentivirus (Figure 10A). Whereas most non-transduced surrounding cells, as well as
385 100% of the TBS²⁷⁵ cells expressing *YFP* were ciliated, only 40% of the Control and

386 TBS²⁷⁵ cells transduced with *LUZP1-YFP* displayed cilia (Figure 10B). Furthermore,
387 we checked the actin cytoskeleton defects observed in TBS²⁷⁵ cells to see the effect of
388 overexpressing *LUZP1-YFP*. Immunostaining showed that *LUZP1-YFP*
389 overexpression led to an increase in F-actin levels both in control and in TBS²⁷⁵ cells
390 compared to the surrounding non-transfected cells or TBS²⁷⁵ cells overexpressing
391 *YFP* (Figure 10C).

392 F-actin has a suppressive effect on ciliogenesis, and CytoD-mediated actin
393 depolymerization has been shown to be permissive to cilia formation in cultured cells
394 (J. Kim et al., 2010). To corroborate the relationship between LUZP1, actin and
395 ciliogenesis, we performed CytoD treatment experiments. We observed that LUZP1-
396 YFP overexpression can counteract the positive effects of CytoD on cilia formation
397 (Figure 10-figure supplement 1). All together, these results support the notion that
398 LUZP1 is a negative regulator of cilia formation and an F-actin stabilizing protein.

399

400

401 **DISCUSSION**

402 We conclude that LUZP1 might be a contributing factor to the TBS phenotype
403 via its interaction with truncated SALL1 and its effect on ciliogenesis, based on
404 several findings: i) LUZP1 levels are reduced in TBS-derived cells likely due to
405 truncated SALL1-mediated degradation through the UPS; ii) LUZP1 interacts with
406 proteins of the centrosome and of the actin cytoskeleton; iii) In the absence of LUZP1,
407 the assembly and growth of primary cilia is enhanced in cycling cells, accompanied
408 by an increase in basal Shh signaling, and the actin cytoskeleton is reduced; iv)
409 Increase of LUZP1 reduces the levels of ciliogenesis in TBS-individuals derived cells.
410 All these results do not rule out the possibility that, in addition to LUZP1, other

411 factors might be contributing to TBS etiology.

412

413 **LUZP1 localizes to the centrosome and actin cytoskeleton**

414 LUZP1 was previously described as a nuclear protein, with expression limited
415 to the mouse brain (Lee et al., 2001; Sun et al., 1996). We tested two different
416 commercial antibodies against LUZP1 by immunofluorescence and, while nuclear
417 localization was sporadic and weak, the most prominent localization of LUZP1 was
418 observed in the actin cytoskeleton and centrosome, both in human and mouse cells.
419 This localization is consistent with our TurboID analysis that showed an enrichment
420 of factors associated with the actin cytoskeleton and/or centrosomes among the
421 potential interactors of LUZP1. The localization of LUZP1 to the actin cytoskeleton,
422 as well as its expression in tissues beyond the brain, is consistent with independent
423 validation in cell lines by the Human Protein Atlas (HPA; proteomics.org) and other
424 expression databases (e.g. EMBL EBI Expression Atlas ebi.ac.uk/gxa). Two
425 independent proximity labeling studies identified LUZP1 as a proximal interactor of
426 centriole (Gupta et al., 2015) and centriolar satellite-related proteins (Gheiratmand et
427 al., 2019). Moreover, LUZP1 has been recently reported as a centrosomal protein
428 involved in cilia regulation (Gonçalves et al., 2019). These localizations are also
429 consistent with fluorescent LUZP1 fusion proteins (this work; (Gupta et al., 2015,
430 Gonçalves, 2019 #117). Discrepancies with the previously reported LUZP1
431 localization and distribution might be due to technical differences, such as epitope
432 specificity for the antisera used in the immunohistochemistry.

433 Here, we report that LUZP1 surrounds the proximal end of both centrioles.
434 Like LUZP1, a large number of centrosomal scaffold proteins contain coiled-coil
435 regions, and the proteins are concentrically localized around a centriole in a highly

436 organized fashion (e.g. Cep120, Cep57, Cep63, Cep152, CPAP, Cdk5Rap2, PCNT)
437 (Fu & Glover, 2012; Lawo et al., 2012; Mennella et al., 2012). Furthermore, we show
438 that LUZP1 interacts with centrosome and actin-related proteins (Figure 3 and Figure
439 4). LUZP1 is associated with CCP110 and CEP97, using pull down,
440 immunoprecipitation and proximity proteomics approaches. This association is likely
441 to be dynamic and potentially indirect, via other bridging factors, since our
442 immunostainings show that LUZP1 and CCP110 are located in different areas of the
443 centrioles. LUZP1 has also been identified as an interactor of ACTR2 (ARP2 actin
444 related protein 2 homologue) and FLNA (Hein et al., 2015; Wang & Nakamura,
445 2019), and it has been recently described as an actin cross-linking protein (Wang &
446 Nakamura, 2019). We found that LUZP1 localizes not only to centrioles and actin
447 cytoskeleton, but also to the midbody in dividing cells, which was recently reported to
448 influence ciliogenesis in polarized epithelial cells (Bernabe-Rubio et al., 2016). Our
449 data suggest that the association of LUZP1 to centrosomes and actin filaments may
450 contribute to its overall roles.

451

452 **LUZP1 as an integrator of actin and primary-cilium dynamics**

453 Actin dynamics coordinate several processes that are crucial for ciliogenesis.
454 For example, positioning the MC to the appropriate area at the cell cortex is an actin-
455 dependent process (Boisvieux-Ulrich et al., 1990; Euteneuer & Schliwa, 1985). A
456 reduction in cortical actin should promote ciliogenesis, since there is less physical
457 restriction for docking of the MC. Supporting this hypothesis, several studies have
458 found that disruptions in the actin cytoskeleton, induced either chemically or
459 genetically, promote ciliogenesis or affect cilia length (Cao et al., 2012; Drummond et
460 al., 2018; Hernandez-Hernandez et al., 2013; G. M. Kang et al., 2015; J. Kim et al.,

461 2015; J. Kim et al., 2010). How actin regulates cilium length is not clear. Recently, a
462 role for actin has been implicated in ectocytosis and cilium tip scission, preventing the
463 axoneme from growing too long (Nager et al., 2017; Phua et al., 2017). Whether
464 LUZP1 at the centrosome is complexed with filamin and actin is unknown, but if so,
465 they could together serve to stabilize the basal body as the axoneme extends or is
466 subjected to mechanical stress.

467

468 **LUZP1 is altered in TBS-derived cells**

469 TBS is caused by mutations in *SALL1* gene, which give rise to truncated
470 proteins that interfere with the normal function of the cell. We show that
471 LUZP1 interacts with truncated SALL1 and with SALL1^{FL}, suggesting that interaction
472 occurs through an N-terminal domain shared by both. In control cells, LUZP1 and
473 SALL1^{FL} likely have minimal or no interaction due to their respective localizations to
474 the cytoplasm and nucleus. However, truncated SALL1, alone or together with
475 SALL1^{FL} that is retained in the cytoplasm, can interact with cytoplasmic LUZP1,
476 promoting its degradation and functional inhibition. Importantly, we detected an
477 increase in LUZP1 levels upon treatment with the proteasome inhibitor MG132
478 (Figure 9), suggesting that LUZP1 degradation is proteasome-dependent. Next, we
479 demonstrated that LUZP1 is ubiquitinated, and that truncated SALL1 both increases
480 LUZP1 ubiquitination and decreases its stability. In agreement with our findings,
481 LUZP1 ubiquitination has been detected in several proteomic screens for
482 ubiquitinated proteins (Akimov et al., 2018; Mertins et al., 2013; Povlsen et al., 2012;
483 Udeshi et al., 2013; Wagner et al., 2012).

484 Further experiments would be required to understand the precise mechanism
485 by which truncated SALL1 can influence LUZP1 ubiquitination, but one possibility

486 could be *de novo* complexes involving specific Ub E3 ligases or de-ubiquitinases
487 which could influence LUZP1 stability. In fact, various E3s/de-ubiquitinases, as well
488 as other components of the UPS, were found as proximal interactors of truncated
489 SALL1 and LUZP1. Furthermore, regulation by the UPS system has been reported for
490 centrosomal factors, including the cilia regulator CCP110 (D'Angiolella et al., 2010;
491 Hossain et al., 2017; Li et al., 2013).

492 Both *Luzp1*^{-/-} and TBS cells showed a reduction in F-actin accompanied by an
493 increase in ciliation. We suggest that the reduction in F-actin in TBS cells might
494 contribute to their higher cilia abundance, longer cilia and increased Shh signaling.
495 An increase in LUZP1 in control and TBS²⁷⁵ cells is sufficient to increase F-actin
496 levels and reduce cilia frequency, supporting that LUZP1 may have a contributing
497 role in the TBS phenotype.

498

499 **The role of LUZP1 in TBS phenotype**

500 Cilia formation, Shh signaling, and the actin cytoskeleton is aberrant in TBS
501 patient-derived fibroblasts (this work; (Bozal-Basterra et al., 2018). Changes in Shh
502 signaling have not been reported in mouse models for TBS, nor in any other cell types
503 or tissues derived from TBS patients. Nevertheless, the phenotypes observed in TBS
504 individuals fall within the spectrum of those observed in ciliopathies, characterized by
505 malformations in digits, ears, heart, brain, kidneys and urogenital anomalies,
506 phenotypes that are consistent with misregulated Shh signaling. Preaxial polydactyly
507 has been associated with ectopic Shh expression in limbs (Dunn et al., 2011; Johnson
508 et al., 2014; Lettice et al., 2003; Lettice et al., 2008; Liem et al., 2009; Zhulyn & Hui,
509 2015); Anal stenosis or imperforate anus have been related to misregulation of Shh
510 pathway (S. Kang et al., 1997; Mo et al., 2001; Roberts et al., 1995), as well as

511 deafness and dysplastic ears (Driver et al., 2008).

512 We observed primary cilia, Shh signaling and cytoskeletal defects in *Luzp1*^{-/-}
513 cells. Several studies have implicated defective primary cilia and Shh signaling in the
514 etiology of neural tube closure defects, as well as crucial roles for the actin
515 cytoskeleton (Wallingford, 2005). There are certain parallels between phenotypes
516 observed in animal models of *Luzp1* and *Sall1*. Exencephaly and neural tube defects
517 were detected in mice and *Xenopus Sall1* mutants (Bohm et al., 2008; Exner et al.,
518 2017; Kiefer et al., 2003). *Luzp1* KO mice exhibit ectopic Shh expression in the
519 hindbrain neuroepithelium and display NTDs, however the expression of Shh-
520 responsive genes (such as *Gli1* or *Ptch1*) was not reported (Hsu et al., 2008). Perhaps
521 the role of LUZP1 in Shh signaling, in spatial control of the signal or the response (or
522 both), contributes to the NTD phenotype. Exencephaly may also be caused by failure
523 in bending at the dorsolateral hinge point of the neural folds, where cells undergo
524 changes in apical actin architecture (Sadler et al., 1982). *Luzp1* KO embryos exhibited
525 dorsolateral neural folds that were convex instead of the concave morphology
526 observed in WT embryos (Hsu et al., 2008), suggested that defective actin dynamics
527 may contribute to the NTD phenotype. Taken together, defective actin dynamics,
528 aberrant primary cilia and changes in Shh signaling might lead to NTDs observed in
529 the LUZP1 mouse model, as well as other animal models of TBS and loss of *Sall*-
530 related proteins.

531 In addition to NTDs, cardiac malformations are another feature found in
532 human ciliopathies (N. T. Klena et al., 2017). Cardiac defects are observed in *Luzp1*
533 knockout mice (Hsu et al., 2008), as well as TBS patients (Kohlhase, 1993). TBS
534 cardiac defects include atrial or ventricular septal defect, the latter of which is seen in
535 *Luzp1* knockout mice. Moreover, compound *Sall1/Sall4* KO mutant mice exhibit both

536 NTDs and cardiac problems (Bohm et al., 2008). While *Luzp1* and *Sall1* may both
537 contribute to neural tube and heart development, a novel crosstalk may arise in TBS
538 due to dominantly-acting truncated SALL1 that could derail these processes and cause
539 deformities.

540

541 In conclusion, our data indicate that LUZP1 functions as a cilia suppressor
542 (Figure 10D). It localizes to actin stress fibers and to the centrosome. In starved cells,
543 likewise in TBS cells, overall LUZP1 levels are diminished in both structures, which
544 facilitates the formation of the primary cilia. In TBS cells, the truncated form of
545 SALL1 localizes to the cytoplasm, interacting with LUZP1 and other factors, leading
546 to the degradation of LUZP1, simulating what happens when control cells undergo
547 starvation. As a result, the frequency of cilia formation increases, and cilia are longer
548 than in control cells.

549 Ciliogenesis requires communication between the actin cytoskeleton and the
550 centrosome. Here, we propose that LUZP1 might contribute as a nexus in this
551 complex intracellular network that is disrupted by truncated SALL1. Our findings
552 point to the intriguing possibility that LUZP1 might be a key relay switch in this
553 network that, together with other factors, might contribute to the phenotypes observed
554 in TBS.

555

556 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

557

558 **Cell culture**

559 TBS-derived primary fibroblasts, U2OS (ATCC HTB-96), HEK 293FT
560 (Invitrogen R70007), and mouse Shh-LIGHT2 cells (Taipale et al., 2000) were

561 cultured at 37°C and 5% CO₂ in Dulbecco's modified Eagle medium (DMEM)
562 supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS, Gibco) and 1%
563 penicillin/streptomycin (Gibco). Human telomerase reverse transcriptase
564 immortalized retinal pigment epithelial cells (hTERT-RPE1, ATCC CRL-4000;
565 designated here as RPE1) were cultured in DMEM:F12 (Gibco) supplemented with
566 10% FBS and 1% penicillin and streptomycin. Dermal fibroblasts carrying the *SALL1*
567 pathogenic variant c.826C>T (*SALL1*^{c.826C>T}), that produce a truncated protein
568 p.Leu275* (*SALL1*²⁷⁵), were derived from a male TBS individual UKTBS#3 (called
569 here TBS²⁷⁵) (Bozal-Basterra et al., 2018). Adult female dermal fibroblasts
570 (ESCTRL#2) from healthy donors were used as controls. Cell lines were
571 authenticated by commercial providers (Invitrogen, ATCC). Additional validation
572 was done by TBS allele genotyping (primary fibroblasts) and reporter selection (zeoR,
573 neoR; Shh-LIGHT2). Cultured cells were maintained between 10 and 20 passages,
574 tested for senescence by γ -H2AX staining and mycoplasma contamination and grown
575 until confluence (6-well plates for RNA extraction and Western blot assays; 10 cm
576 dishes for pulldowns). The use of human samples in this study was approved by the
577 institutional review board (Ethics Committee at CIC bioGUNE, protocol P-CBG-
578 CBBA-2111) and appropriate informed consent was obtained from human subjects or
579 their parents.

580

581 **Cell synchronization and drug treatment**

582 RPE1 cells were arrested in G1 phase by treatment with mimosine (Sigma,
583 400 μ M) for 24 hours. For S phase arrest, cells were subjected to thymidine treatment
584 (Sigma, 2.5 mM) for 16 hours, followed by release for 8 hours, and subsequently
585 blocked again for 16 hours. For G2/M phase arrest, cells were treated with RO-3306

586 (Sigma, 10 μ M) for 20 hours. For G0 phase synchronization and inducing primary
587 cilia formation, cells were starved for 48 hours (DMEM, 0% FBS, 1% penicillin and
588 streptomycin). Treatments with the proteasome inhibitor MG132 (Calbiochem, 5 μ M)
589 were for 15 hours and with CytoD (Sigma, 50 nM) for 16 hours to stimulate actin
590 depolymerization. HEK 293FT cells were transfected using calcium phosphate
591 method and U2OS cells using Effectene Transfection Reagent (Qiagen).

592

593 **CRISPR-Cas9 genome editing**

594 CRISPR-Cas9 targeting of *SALL1* locus was performed to generate a HEK 293FT cell
595 line carrying a TBS-like allele (Bozal-Basterra et al., 2018). The mouse *Luzp1* locus
596 was targeted in NIH3T3-based Shh-LIGHT2 fibroblasts (Taipale et al., 2000) (kind
597 gift of A. McGee, Imperial College). These are NIH3T3 mouse fibroblasts that carry
598 an incorporated Shh reporter (firefly luciferase under control of *Gli3*-responsive
599 promoter). Cas9 was introduced into Shh-LIGHT2 cells by lentiviral transduction
600 (Lenti-Cas9-blast; Addgene #52962; kind gift of F. Zhang, MIT) and selection with
601 blasticidin (5 μ g/ml). Two high-scoring sgRNAs were selected (<http://crispr.mit.edu/>)
602 to target near the initiation codon (sg2: 5'-CTTAAATCGCAGGTGGCGGT_TGG-3';
603 sg3: 5'-CTTCAATCTTCAGTACCCGC_TGG-3'). These sequences were cloned into
604 px459 2.0 (Addgene #62988; kind gift of F. Zhang, MIT), for expressing both
605 sgRNAs and additional Cas9 with puromycin selection. Transfections were performed
606 in Shh-LIGHT2/Cas9 cells with Lipofectamine 3000 (Thermo). 24 hours after
607 transfection, transient puromycin selection (0.5 μ g/ml) was applied for 48 hours to
608 enrich for transfected cells. Cells were plated at clonal density, and well-isolated
609 clones were picked and propagated individually. Western blotting was used to identify
610 clones lacking *Luzp1* expression. Further propagation of a selected clone (#6) was

611 carried out with G418 (0.4 mg/ml) and zeocin (0.15 mg/ml) selection to maintain
612 expression of luciferase reporters. Genotyping was performed using genomic PCR
613 (*MmLuzp1_geno_for*: 5'-GTTGCCAAAGAAGGTTGTGGATGCC-3';
614 *MmLuzp1_geno_rev*: 5'-CGTAAGGTTTTCTTCCTCTTCAAGTTTCTC-3'). We
615 found that *Luzp1*^{-/-} cells presented a homozygous deletion of the sequence: 5'-
616 ccacctgcgatttaagttacagagcctgagccgccgcctcgatgagtagaggaagctacaaaaaacctccagagagcag
617 aggatgagctcctggacctccaggacaaggtgatccaggcagagggcagcgactccagcagcgtggctgagatcgaggt
618 gctgcgccagcgg-3'. This generated a truncation and a stop codon early in the N-
619 terminal part of the protein. The resulting peptide was: MAELTNYKDAASNRY*. A
620 rescue cell line was generated by transducing Shh-LIGHT2 *Luzp1* KO clone #6 with a
621 lentiviral expression vector carrying EFS-LUZP1-YFP-P2A-blast^R, with a positive
622 population selected by fluorescence-activated cell sorting.

623

624 **Plasmid construction**

625 *SALL1* truncated (*SALL1*²⁷⁵-YFP or Myc-BirA*-*SALL1*²⁷⁵) and FL versions (*SALL1*^{FL}-
626 YFP, *SALL1*^{FL}-2xHA or Myc-BirA*-*SALL1*^{FL}) were previously described (Bozal-
627 Bastera et al., 2018). Human *LUZP1* ORF was amplified by high-fidelity PCR
628 (Platinum SuperFi; Thermo) from RPE1 cell cDNA and cloned to generate *CB6-GFP*-
629 *LUZP1*. This was used as a source clone to generate additional variants, including
630 *CMV-LUZP1-YFP*. The LUZP1-YFP and TbID-LUZP1 lentiviral expression vectors
631 were generated by replacing Cas9 in Lenti-Cas9-blast (Addgene #52962). All
632 constructs were verified by Sanger sequencing. Plasmids *CAG*-
633 *BioUBC(x4)_BirA_V5_puro* (called here BioUb) and *CAG-BirA-puro* (called here
634 BirA) were reported previously (Pirone et al., 2017).

635

636 **Biotin pulldowns**

637 Using the BioID and the TurboID methods (Branon et al., 2018; Roux et al., 2012),
638 proteins in close proximity to SALL1 and LUZP1, respectively, were biotinylated and
639 isolated by streptavidin-bead pulldowns. For transient transfections, *Myc-BirA**-
640 *SALL1^{c.826C>T}* or *Myc-BirA*-SALL1FL* were used in HEK 293FT cells (10 cm dishes).
641 For TurboID experiments, *TbID-LUZP1-P2A-blast* or *TbID-P2A-blast* alone were
642 transduced in RPE1 cells and a stable population was selected. For the isolation of
643 BioUb-conjugates 10 cm dishes were transfected with BioUb or BirA as control
644 (Pirone et al., 2017). Briefly, 24 hours after transfection, medium was supplemented
645 with biotin at 50 μ M. Cells were collected 48 hours after transfection, washed 3 times
646 on ice with cold phosphate buffered saline (PBS) and scraped in lysis buffer [8 M urea,
647 1% SDS, 1x protease inhibitor cocktail (Roche), 60 μ M NEM in 1x PBS; 1 ml per 10
648 cm dish]. At room temperature, samples were sonicated and cleared by centrifugation.
649 Cell lysates were incubated overnight with 40 μ l of equilibrated NeutrAvidin-agarose
650 beads (Thermo Scientific). Beads were subjected to stringent washes using the
651 following washing buffers (WB), all prepared in PBS: WB1 (8 M urea, 0.25% SDS);
652 WB2 (6 M Guanidine-HCl); WB3 (6.4 M urea, 1 M NaCl, 0.2% SDS), WB4 (4 M
653 urea, 1 M NaCl, 10% isopropanol, 10% ethanol and 0.2% SDS); WB5 (8 M urea, 1%
654 SDS); and WB6 (2% SDS). For elution of biotinylated proteins, beads were heated at
655 99°C in 50 μ l of Elution Buffer (4x Laemmli buffer, 100 mM DTT). Beads were
656 separated by centrifugation (18000 x g, 5 minutes).

657

658 **Lentiviral transduction**

659 Lentiviral expression constructs were packaged using psPAX2 and pVSV-G
660 (Addgene) in HEK 293FT cells, and lentiviral supernatants were used to transduce

661 Shh-LIGHT2 cells, RPE1 cells, or TBS²⁷⁵ and control human fibroblasts. Stable-
662 expressing populations were selected using puromycin (1 µg/ml) or blasticidin (5
663 µg/ml). The vectors EFS-LUZP1-YFP-P2A-blast^R, EFS-YFP-P2A-blast^R, LL-GFS-
664 SALL1^{c.826C>T}-IRES-puro^R, LL-GFS-stop-IRES-puro^R, EFS-TbID-LUZP1-P2A-
665 blast^R and EFS-TbID-P2A-blast^R were used. Lentiviral supernatants were
666 concentrated 100-fold before use (Lenti-X concentrator, Clontech). Concentrated
667 virus was used for transducing primary fibroblasts and RPE1 cells.

668

669 **Mass spectrometry**

670 Analysis was done in RPE1 cells stably expressing TbID or TbID-LUZP1 at
671 sub-endogenous levels. Three independent pulldown experiments (1.5x10⁸ cells per
672 replicate) were analyzed by MS. Samples eluted from the NeutrAvidin beads were
673 separated in SDS-PAGE (50% loaded) and stained with Sypro-Ruby (Biorad)
674 according to manufacturer's instructions. Entire gel lanes were excised, divided into
675 pieces and in-gel digested with trypsin. Recovered peptides were desalted using stage-
676 tip C18 microcolumns (Zip-tip, Millipore) and resuspended in 0.1% FA prior to MS
677 analysis. Samples were analyzed in a novel hybrid trapped ion mobility spectrometry
678 – quadrupole time of flight mass spectrometer (timsTOF Pro with PASEF, Bruker
679 Daltonics) coupled online to a nanoElute liquid chromatograph (Bruker). This mass
680 spectrometer takes advantage of a novel scan mode termed parallel accumulation –
681 serial fragmentation (PASEF), which multiplies the sequencing speed without any
682 loss in sensitivity (Meier et al., 2015), providing outstanding analytical speed and
683 sensibility for proteomics analyses (Meier et al., 2018). Sample (200 ng) was directly
684 loaded in a 15 cm Bruker nanoelute FIFTEEN C18 analytical column (Bruker) and
685 resolved at 400 nl/min with a 100 min gradient. Column was heated to 50°C using an

686 oven. Protein identification and quantification was carried out using PEAKS software
687 (Bioinformatics solutions). Searches were carried out against a database consisting of
688 human entries (Uniprot/Swissprot), with precursor and fragment tolerances of 20 ppm
689 and 0.05 Da. Only proteins identified with at least two peptides at FDR<5% were
690 considered for further analysis. Data was loaded onto Perseus platform (Tyanova et
691 al., 2016) and further processed (Log₂ transformation, selection of proteins with at
692 least two valid values in at least one condition, imputation). A t-test was applied in
693 order to determine the statistical significance of the differences detected, and
694 heatmaps were generated using this tool. Protein IDs were ranked according to the
695 number of peptides found and their corresponding intensities. Gene ontology (GO)
696 term enrichment was analyzed using g:GOSt Profiler, a tool integrated in the
697 g:Profiler web server (Reimand et al., 2016). GO enrichment was obtained by
698 calculating $-\text{Log}_{10}$ of the P-value.

699 Network analysis of LUZP1 interactors was performed using the String app
700 version 1.4.2 in Cytoscape version 3.7.2, with a high confidence interaction score
701 (0.7). Transparency and width of the edges were continuously mapped to the String
702 score (textmining, databases, coexpression, experiments, fusion, neighborhood and
703 cooccurrence). Color, transparency and size of the nodes were discretely mapped to
704 the Log₂ enrichment value as described in Figure 1. The Molecular COmplex
705 DEtection (MCODE) plug-in version 1.5.1 was used to identify highly connected
706 subclusters of proteins (degree cutoff of 2; Cluster finding: Haircut; Node score cutoff
707 of 0.5 ; K-Core of 2 ; Max. Depth of 100).

708

709 **GFP-trap pulldowns**

710 All steps were performed at 4°C. HEK 293FT transfected cells were collected

711 after 48 hours, washed 3 times with 1x PBS and lysed in 1 ml of lysis buffer [25 mM
712 Tris-HCl pH 7.5, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40, 0.5% Triton X-100, 5%
713 glycerol, protease inhibitors (Roche)]. Lysates were kept on ice for 30 minutes
714 vortexing every 5 minutes and spun down at 25,000 x g for 20 minutes. After saving
715 40 µl of supernatant (input), the rest was incubated overnight with 30 µl of pre-
716 washed GFP-Trap resin (Chromotek) in a rotating wheel. Beads were washed 5 times
717 for 5 minutes each with WB (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.5, 300 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA,
718 1% NP-40, 0.5% TX-100, 5% glycerol). Beads were centrifuged at 2,000 x g for 2
719 minutes after each wash. For elution, samples were boiled for 5 minutes at 95°C in 2x
720 Laemmli buffer.

721

722 **Immunoprecipitation**

723 All steps were performed at 4°C. Cells were collected and lysates were
724 processed as described for GFP-trap pulldowns. After saving 40 µl of supernatant
725 (input), the rest was incubated overnight with 1 µg of anti-CEP97 antibody
726 (Proteintech), or anti-LUZP1 antibody (Sigma HPA028506) and for additional 4
727 hours with 40 µl of pre-washed Protein G Sepharose 4 Fast Flow beads (GE
728 Healthcare) on a rotating wheel. Beads were washed 5 times for 5 minutes each with
729 WB (10 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.5, 137 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% Triton X-100).
730 Beads were centrifuged at 2,000 x g for 2 minutes after each wash. For elution,
731 samples were boiled for 5 minutes at 95°C in 2x Laemmli buffer.

732

733 **Western blot analysis**

734 Cells were lysed in cold RIPA buffer (Cell Signaling Technology), WB5 (8 M
735 urea, 1% SDS) or weak buffer (10 mM PIPES pH 6.8, 100 mM NaCl, 1 mM EGTA, 3

736 mM MgCl₂, 300 mM sucrose, 0.5 mM DTT, 1% Triton X-100) supplemented with 1x
737 protease/phosphatase inhibitor cocktail (Roche). Lysates were kept on ice for 30
738 minutes vortexing every 5 minutes and then cleared by centrifugation (25,000 x g, 20
739 minutes, 4°C). Supernatants were collected and protein content was quantified by
740 BCA protein quantification assay (Pierce). After SDS-PAGE and transfer to
741 nitrocellulose membranes, blocking was performed in 5% milk, or in 5% BSA
742 (Bovine Serum Albumin, Fraction V, Sigma) in PBT (1x PBS, 0.1% Tween-20). In
743 general, primary antibodies were incubated overnight at 4°C and secondary antibodies
744 for 1 hour at room temperature (RT). Antibodies used: rabbit anti-LUZP1
745 (Proteintech, 1:1,000) for Figure 1 and rabbit anti-LUZP1 (Sigma HPA028506,
746 1:1,000) for the rest of the experiments, rabbit anti-CCP110 (Proteintech, 1:1,000),
747 rabbit anti-CEP97 (Proteintech, 1:1,000), mouse anti-GFP (Roche, 1:1,000), mouse
748 anti-GAPDH (Proteintech, 1:1,000), mouse anti-FLNA (Merck, 1:1,000), rabbit anti-
749 BirA (Sino Biological, 1:1000), HRP-conjugated anti-biotin (Cell Signaling
750 Technology, 1:2,000), rabbit anti Myc (Cell Signaling Technology, 1:2,000), mouse
751 anti-actin (Sigma, 1:1,000), goat anti-GLI3 (R&D, 1:1,000) and mouse anti-SALL1
752 (R&D, 1:1,000). Secondary antibodies were anti-mouse or anti-rabbit HRP-
753 conjugates (Jackson Immunoresearch). Proteins were detected using Clarity ECL
754 (BioRad) or Super Signal West Femto (Pierce). Quantification of bands was
755 performed using ImageJ software and normalized against GAPDH or actin levels. At
756 least three independent blots were quantified per experiment.

757

758 **Immunostaining**

759 Shh-LIGHT2 cells, RPE1, U2OS cells and primary fibroblasts from control
760 and TBS individuals were seeded on 11 mm coverslips (15,000-25,000 cells per well;

761 24well plate). After washing 3 times with cold 1xPBS, cells were fixed with 100%
762 methanol for 10 minutes at -20°C or with 4% PFA supplemented with 0.1% Triton X-
763 100 in PBS for 15 minutes at RT. Then, coverslips were washed 3 times with 1x PBS.
764 Blocking was performed for 1 hour at 37°C in blocking buffer (BB: 2% fetal calf
765 serum, 1% BSA in 1x PBS). Primary antibodies were incubated overnight at 4°C and
766 cells were washed with 1x PBS 3 times. To label the ciliary axoneme and the basal
767 body/pericentriolar region, we used mouse antibodies against acetylated alpha-tubulin
768 (Santa Cruz Biotechnologies, 1:160) and gamma-tubulin (Proteintech, 1:160). Other
769 antibodies include: rat anti-Centrin-2 (CETN2, Biolegend, 1:160), rabbit anti-LUZP1
770 (Sigma HPA028506, 1:100), rabbit anti-CCP110 (Proteintech, 1:200), rabbit anti-
771 PCM1 (Cell Signaling Technology, 1:100), rabbit anti ODF2 (Atlas, 1:100), mouse
772 anti-CEP164 (Genetex, 1:100), mouse anti beta-tubulin (DSHB, 1:100) and
773 pericentrin (Abcam, 1:100).

774 Donkey anti-rat, anti-mouse or anti-rabbit secondary antibodies (Jackson
775 Immunoresearch) conjugated to Alexa 488, Alexa 594 or Alexa 633 (1:200), GFP-
776 booster (Chromotek, 1:500), Alexa-594-conjugated Streptavidin (Jackson
777 Immunoresearch, 1:100) and Alexa 568-conjugated phalloidin (Invitrogen, 1:500),
778 were incubated for 1 hour at 37°C, followed by nuclear staining with DAPI (10
779 minutes, 300 ng/ml in PBS; Sigma). Fluorescence imaging was performed using an
780 upright wide-field fluorescent microscope (Axioimager D1, Zeiss) or super-resolution
781 microscopy (Leica SP8 Lightning and Zeiss LSM 880 Fast Airyscan) with 63x Plan
782 ApoChromat NA1.4. For cilia measurements and counting, primary cilia from at least
783 fifteen different fluorescent micrographs taken for each experimental condition were
784 analyzed using the ruler tool from Adobe Photoshop. Cilia frequency was obtained
785 dividing the number of total cilia by the number of nuclei on each micrograph.

786 Number of cells per micrograph was similar in both TBS and control fibroblasts. To
787 estimate the level of fluorescence in a determined region, we used the mean intensity
788 obtained by ImageJ. To obtain the signal histograms on Figure 2C-D, we used the plot
789 profile tool in FIJI.

790

791 **qRT-PCR analysis**

792 Shh-LIGHT2 cells were starved for 48 hours. Total RNA was obtained with
793 EZNA Total RNA Kit (Omega) and quantified by Nanodrop spectrophotometer.
794 cDNAs were prepared using the SuperScript III First-Strand Synthesis System
795 (Invitrogen) in 10 µl volume per reaction. *LUZP1*, *GAPDH*, *Gli1*, *Ptch1*, and *Rplp0*
796 primers were tested for efficiency and products checked for correct size before being
797 used in test samples. qPCR was done using PerfeCTa SYBR Green SuperMix Low
798 (Quantabio). Reactions were performed in 10 µl, adding 1 µl of cDNA and 0.5 µl of
799 each primer (10 µM), in a CFX96 thermocycler (BioRad) using the following
800 protocol: 95°C for 10 minutes and 40 cycles of 95°C for 10 seconds and 55-60°C for
801 30 seconds. Melting curve analysis was performed for each pair of primers between
802 65°C and 95°C, with 0.5°C temperature increments every 5 seconds. Relative gene
803 expression data were analyzed using the $\Delta\Delta C_t$ method. Reactions were done in
804 triplicates and results were derived from at least three independent experiments
805 normalized to *GAPDH* and *Rplp0* and presented as relative expression levels. Primer
806 sequences: *LUZP1-F*: 5'-GGAATCGGGTAGGAGACACCA-3'; *LUZP1-R*: 5'-
807 TTCCCAGGCAGTTCAGACGGA-3; *GAPDH-F*: 5'-
808 AGCCACATCGCTCAGACAC-3'; *GAPDH-R*: 5'-GCCCAATACGACCAAATCC-
809 3'; *Gli1-F*: 5'-AGCCTTCAGCAATGCCAGTGAC-3'; *Gli1-R*: 5'-
810 GTCAGGACCATGCACTGTCTTG-3'; *Ptch1-F*: 5'-

811 AAGCCGACTACATGCCAGAG-3'; *Ptch1-R*: 5'-
812 TGATGCCATCTGCGTCTACCAG-3', *Rplp0-F*: 5'-
813 ACTGGTCTAGGACCCGAGAAG-3'; *Rplp0-R*: 5'-CTCCCACCTTGTCTCCAGTC-
814 3'.

815

816 **Luciferase assays**

817 Shh-LIGHT2 cells were starved for 48h, and treated or not for the last 24
818 hours with purmorphamine (5 μ M, ChemCruz) to induce Shh signaling pathway.
819 Firefly luciferase expression was measured using the Dual-Luciferase Reporter Assay
820 System (Promega) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Luminescence was
821 measured and data were normalized to the Renilla luciferase readout. For each
822 construct, luciferase activity upon purmorphamine treatment was divided by the
823 activity of cells before treatment to obtain the fold change value. Experiments were
824 performed with both biological (n=3) and technical (n=6) replicates.

825

826 **Statistical analysis**

827 Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad 6.0 software. Data were
828 analyzed by Shapiro-Wilk normality test and Levene's test of variance. We used two-
829 tailed unpaired Student's t-test or Mann Whitney-U tests for comparing two groups,
830 One-way ANOVA or Kruskal-Wallis and the corresponding post-hoc tests for more
831 than two groups and two-way ANOVA to compare more than one variable in more
832 than two groups. P values were represented by asterisks as follows: (*) P-value <
833 0.05; (**) P-value < 0.01; (***) P-value < 0.001; (****) P-value < 0.0001.
834 Differences were considered significant when $P < 0.05$. Values used for graphical
835 representations and statistical analysis are available in Source Data 2.

836

837

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855

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857 **COMPETING INTERESTS**

858 The authors declare no competing interests.

859

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1194

1195

1196 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

1197

1198 **Figure 1. Proximity proteomics reveal LUZP1 interaction with truncated SALL1**
1199 **and with centrosome- and actin cytoskeleton-associated proteins.** (A) Western
1200 blot analysis of BioID, streptavidin pulldown (PD) of HEK 293FT cells transfected
1201 with Myc-tagged BirA*-SALL1²⁷⁵ or BirA*-SALL1^{FL}. Specific antibodies (LUZP1,
1202 actin, Myc) were used as indicated. Anti-Myc antibody detected the self-biotinylated
1203 form of BirA*-SALL1^{FL} (asterisk) or BirA*-SALL1²⁷⁵ (black arrowhead). (B)
1204 STRING core cluster network analysis of LUZP1 interactors (confidence 0.7 or
1205 higher), visualized using Cytoscape software. Color and size of the nodes indicate
1206 Log₂ of the TurboID-LUZP1 (TbID-LUZP1) *versus* TbID alone ratio. The most
1207 highly interconnected clusters, centrosome and actin, are indicated separately. (C)
1208 Volcano plot representing the distribution of the candidates identified by proximity
1209 proteomics in three independent experiments. Proteins with more than 1-fold change
1210 in TbID-LUZP1 intensity with respect to the TbID (Log₂ ≥ 0) were considered as
1211 LUZP1-associated candidates (grey dots). Proteins associated with the actin
1212 cytoskeleton and the centrosome were colored in green and pink colors, respectively.
1213 (D) Graphical representation of the -Log₁₀ of the *p*-value for each of the represented
1214 GO terms of the TbID experiment performed on RPE1 stably expressing near
1215 endogenous levels of TbID-LUZP1 *vs* TbID. Pink dotted line represents the cutoff of
1216 *p*-value <0.01.

1217 The following figure supplement is available for Figure 1:

1218 Figure 1-figure supplement 1. Full western blot images for Figure 1.

1219 Figure 1-figure supplement 2. Analysis of TbID constructs expression and
1220 biotinylation localization.

1221

1222 **Figure 2. LUZP1 localizes to the centrosome and the actin cytoskeleton. (A)**

1223 Immunofluorescence micrographs of LUZP1 (green) and Centrin-2 (CETN2, blue) in

1224 RPE1 cells. **(B-D)** Immunofluorescence micrographs of U2OS cells expressing

1225 *LUZP1-YFP* (green) stained with antibodies against CETN2 (blue) and CCP110 **(B)**,

1226 Pericentrin **(C)** and PCM1 **(D)** in magenta. Plot profile of the different fluorophore

1227 intensities along the yellow lines in **(C, D)**. Schematic representation of LUZP1

1228 localization at the centrosome according to their respective micrographs in **(A-D)**.

1229 Scale bar, 1 μ m. Imaging in **(A-D)** was performed using confocal microscopy (Leica

1230 SP8, 63x objective). Lightning software (Leica) was applied. **(E, F)**

1231 Immunofluorescence micrographs of U2OS cells stained with an antibody against

1232 endogenous LUZP1 (green), phalloidin to detect F-actin (magenta), and

1233 counterstained with DAPI (blue). Single green and magenta channels are shown in

1234 black and white. **(F)** LUZP1 at the midbody in dividing cells (yellow arrowhead).

1235 Scale bar, 10 μ m **(E, F)**. Imaging in **(E, F)** was performed using widefield

1236 fluorescence microscopy (Zeiss Axioimager D1, 63x objective)

1237 The following figure supplement is available for Figure 2:

1238 Figure 2-figure supplement 1. Centrosomal localization of LUZP1 at different cell

1239 cycle stages.

1240 Figure 2-video 1. LUZP1 localization in the centrosome.

1241

1242 **Figure 3. TBS cells show reduced LUZP1 levels at the centrosome. (A, B)**

1243 Immunofluorescence micrographs of non-starved and starved human-derived Control

1244 **(A)** and TBS²⁷⁵ fibroblasts **(B)** stained with antibodies against endogenous LUZP1

1245 (green, yellow arrowheads), Centrin-2 (CETN2, blue) and acetylated alpha-tubulin

1246 (magenta). Black and white images show the isolated green channel. Note the
1247 reduction of LUZP1 in starved cells and in non-starved TBS²⁷⁵ compared to non-
1248 starved control fibroblasts. Imaging was performed using widefield fluorescence
1249 microscopy (Zeiss Axioimager D1, 63x objective). Scale bar, 4 μ m. (C) Graphical
1250 representation of the LUZP1 mean intensities (left panel) or the centrosome area
1251 (right panel), corresponding to the experiments shown in (A-B); $n \geq 6$ micrographs.
1252 Three independent experiments were pooled together. *P*-values were calculated using
1253 the unpaired two-tailed Student's test or U- Mann-Whitney test. (D) Western blot of
1254 inputs (lanes 1 to 4) and GFP-Trap pulldowns (lines 5 to 8) performed in WT HEK
1255 293FT cells or in 293³³⁵ *SALL1* mutant cells transfected with *LUZP1-YFP* (lanes 1, 3,
1256 5 and 7) or *YFP* alone (lanes 2, 4, 6 and 8). Numbers under CCP110 and CEP97
1257 panels result from dividing band intensities of each pulldown by their respective input
1258 levels. GAPDH was used as loading control. (E, F) Co-immunoprecipitation
1259 experiments show LUZP1-CCP110 (E) and CEP97-LUZP1 (F) interactions. Rabbit
1260 IgG was used for immunoprecipitation controls. GAPDH was used as loading and
1261 specificity control. In all panels, specific antibodies (LUZP1, GAPDH, CCP110,
1262 CEP97, GFP) were used as indicated. Blots shown here are representative of three
1263 independent experiments. Molecular weight markers are shown to the right.

1264 The following figure supplement is available for Figure 3:

1265 Figure 3-figure supplement 1. Full western blot images for Figure 3.

1266

1267 **Figure 4. Reduction in LUZP1 coincides with decreased F-actin.** (A)

1268 Immunofluorescence micrographs of Control and TBS²⁷⁵ human fibroblasts stained
1269 with an antibody against endogenous LUZP1 (green), phalloidin to label F-actin
1270 (magenta), and counterstained with DAPI to label the nuclei (blue). Black and white

1271 images show the single green and magenta channels. Note the overall reduction in
1272 LUZP1 and F-actin levels in TBS²⁷⁵ compared to control fibroblasts. Scale bar, 10 μ m.
1273 Imaging was performed using widefield fluorescence microscopy (Zeiss Axioimager
1274 D1, 63x objective). **(B, C)** Graphical representation of the LUZP1 **(B)** and F-actin **(C)**
1275 mean intensities, corresponding to the experiments shown in **(A)**; $n \geq 6$ micrographs.
1276 Three independent experiments were pooled together. *P*-values were calculated using
1277 the unpaired two-tailed Student's test or U- Mann-Whitney test. **(D)** Western blot of
1278 inputs or GFP-Trap pulldowns performed in HEK 293FT cells transfected with
1279 *LUZP1-YFP* or *YFP* alone. Anti-GFP antibody detected YFP alone (two black
1280 arrowheads) and LUZP1-YFP (two white arrowheads). Blots shown here are
1281 representative of three independent experiments. Molecular weight markers are
1282 shown to the right. Specific antibodies (LUZP1, GAPDH, CCP110, CEP97, GFP)
1283 were used as indicated. **(E)** Western blot of total cell lysates of HEK 293FT treated or
1284 not with cytochalasin D (CytoD) in a mild lysis buffer (TX-100 0.1%, lanes 1, 2) or a
1285 strong lysis buffer (WB5, lanes 3, 4). Note the increase in LUZP1 levels upon actin
1286 polymerization blockage with CytoD, exclusively when cells were lysed on 01% TX-
1287 100-based lysis buffer. GAPDH was used as loading control. In **(D)** and **(E)** panels,
1288 specific antibodies (LUZP1, GAPDH, actin, FLNA, GFP) were used as indicated. **(F)**
1289 Graphical representation of LUZP1 vs GAPDH band intensities in **(E)** normalized to
1290 lane 1. Graphs represent Mean and SEM of three independent experiments. *P*-value
1291 was calculated using two tailed unpaired Student's t-test. Molecular weight markers
1292 in **(D)** and **(E)** are shown to the right.

1293 The following figure supplement is available for Figure 4:

1294 Figure 4-figure supplement 1. Full western blot images for Figure 4.

1295

1296 **Figure 5. Generation of LUZP1 mutant cells.** (A, B) Immunofluorescence
1297 micrographs of Shh-LIGHT2 control cells (WT), *Luzp1* depleted Shh-LIGHT2 cells
1298 (*Luzp1*^{-/-}) and *Luzp1*^{-/-} cells rescued with human *LUZP1* (+LUZP1 cells) stained with
1299 a specific antibody against endogenous LUZP1 (green) and DAPI (blue) (A) or
1300 gamma-tubulin (magenta) (B). Single green and magenta channels are shown in black
1301 and white. Scale bars, 10 μm (A) or 2.5 μm (B). Images were taken using widefield
1302 fluorescence microscopy (Zeiss Axioimager D1, 63x objective). Note the lack of
1303 LUZP1 in *Luzp1*^{-/-} cells. (C) Western blot analysis of total lysates of WT, *Luzp1*^{-/-}
1304 and +LUZP1 cells using anti-LUZP1 antibodies. Molecular weight markers are
1305 shown to the right. Note the lack of LUZP1 signal in *Luzp1*^{-/-} cells by
1306 immunofluorescence and Western blot

1307 The following figure supplement is available for Figure 5:

1308 Figure 5-figure supplement 1. Full western blot images for Figure 5.

1309

1310 **Figure 6. Loss of *Luzp1* causes aberrant cilia frequency and length and Shh**
1311 **signaling.** (A) Micrographs of Shh-LIGHT2 cells (WT), Shh-LIGHT2 cells lacking
1312 *Luzp1* (*Luzp1*^{-/-}) and *Luzp1*^{-/-} cells rescued with human *LUZP1-YFP* (+LUZP1)
1313 analyzed in cycling conditions (non-starved), or during cilia assembly (48 hours
1314 starved). Cilia were visualized by acetylated alpha-tubulin (magenta), basal body by
1315 ODF2 (green) and nuclei by DAPI (blue). Scale bar 2.5 μm. (B, C) Graphical
1316 representation of percentage of ciliated cells per micrograph (B) and cilia length (C)
1317 measured in WT (blue circles, n>34 micrographs), *Luzp1*^{-/-} (orange circles, n>44
1318 micrographs) or +LUZP1 cells (green circles, n>30 micrographs) from three
1319 independent experiments. No starvation: WT 2.3 μm; *Luzp1*^{-/-} cells 3.0 μm; +LUZP1
1320 cells 2.9 μm; 48 hours starvation: WT 4.2 μm; *Luzp1*^{-/-} cells 4.1 μm; +LUZP1 cells

1321 4.8 μm ; all average measures. **(D)** Immunofluorescence micrographs of WT and
1322 LUZP1^{-/-} cells stained with antibodies against endogenous CCP110 (green), gamma-
1323 tubulin (gTub) to label the centrioles (magenta) and DAPI to label the nuclei (blue).
1324 Black and white images show the single green and magenta channels. Note the
1325 different distribution of CCP110 to the centrosome in LUZP1^{-/-} compared to WT cells.
1326 Scale bar, 1 μm . **(E)** Graphical representation of the percentage of cells showing the
1327 presence of CCP110 to both centrioles per micrograph corresponding to the
1328 experiments in **(D)**; n=10 micrographs. Three independent experiments were pooled
1329 together.

1330

1331 **Figure 7. *Luzp1*^{-/-} cells show aberrant Shh signaling.** **(A, B)** Graphical
1332 representation of the fold-change in the expression of *Gli1* (n=5) **(A)** and *Ptch1* (n=7)
1333 **(B)** obtained by qRT-PCR from wild-type Shh-LIGHT2 cells (WT; blue dots) or Shh-
1334 LIGHT2 cells lacking *Luzp1* (*Luzp1*^{-/-}; orange dots), treated (+) or not (-) with
1335 purmorphamine for 24 hours. **(C)** Western blot analysis of lysates from WT and
1336 *Luzp1*^{-/-} cells. Samples were probed against GLI3 using an antibody that detects both
1337 GLI3-activator form (GLI3-A) and GLI3-repressor form (GLI3-R); GAPDH was used
1338 as loading control. Numbers under the lanes are the Mean of 3 independent
1339 experiments, resulting of dividing the activator by the repressor intensities, taking WT
1340 non-induced value as 1. Molecular weight markers are shown to the right. **(D, E)**
1341 Graphical representation of fold-change in luciferase activation when WT (n>7; blue
1342 dots), *Luzp1*^{-/-} (n>7; orange dots) or +LUZP1 (n=4; green dots) cells are treated for 6
1343 and 24 hours or not (-) with purmorphamine. **(E)** Each treated condition was
1344 normalized against its respective non treated condition, taking the non-induced value
1345 as 1 (dashed line). All graphs represent the Mean and SEM. *P*-values were calculated

1346 using two-tailed unpaired Student's t-test or One-way ANOVA and Bonferroni post-
1347 hoc test.

1348 The following figure supplement is available for Figure 7:

1349 Figure 7-figure supplement 1. Full western blot images for Figure 7

1350

1351 **Figure 8. Cells missing Luzp1 show reduced F-actin levels. (A)**

1352 Immunofluorescence micrographs of WT, Luzp1^{-/-} and +LUZP1 cells stained with an
1353 antibody against endogenous LUZP1 (green), phalloidin to detect F-actin (magenta),
1354 and counterstained with DAPI (blue). Single green and magenta channels are shown
1355 in black and white. Note the lack of LUZP1 signal in Luzp1^{-/-} cells. Scale bar, 10 μm.

1356 **(B)** Immunofluorescence micrographs of non-starved and starved WT cells stained
1357 with antibodies against endogenous LUZP1 (green), phalloidin (magenta) and DAPI
1358 (blue). Single green and magenta channels are shown in black and white. Scale bar, 5
1359 μm. Imaging was performed using widefield fluorescence microscopy (Zeiss
1360 Axioimager D1, 63x objective). **(C)** Graphical representation of the LUZP1 or F-actin
1361 mean intensity (arbitrary units) as shown in **(B)**. Graphs represent Mean and SEM of
1362 three independent experiments pooled together. *P*-values were calculated using One-
1363 way ANOVA and Bonferroni post-hoc test

1364

1365 **Figure 9. Truncated SALL1 leads to LUZP1 degradation through the UPS. (A)**

1366 Representative Western blot of Control and TBS²⁷⁵ total cell lysates treated or not
1367 with MG132. A specific antibody detected endogenous LUZP1, and GAPDH was
1368 used as loading control. **(B)** Graphical representation of the fold changes of
1369 LUZP1/GAPDH ratios obtained in **(A)** for of Control (blue dots) and TBS²⁷⁵ (orange
1370 dots) treated (+) or not (-) with the proteasome inhibitor MG132. Note the increase of

1371 LUZP1 until reaching control levels in TBS²⁷⁵ cells upon MG132 treatment. (C)
1372 Representative Western blot of 293^{WT} and 293³³⁵ total cell lysates treated or not with
1373 MG132. A specific antibody against LUZP1 detected endogenous LUZP1, and
1374 GAPDH was used as loading control. (D) Graphical representation of the fold
1375 changes of LUZP1/GAPDH ratios obtained in panel C for 293^{WT} (blue dots) and
1376 293³³⁵ (orange dots) treated (+) or not (-) with MG132. Note that LUZP1 in 293³³⁵
1377 reaches control levels with MG132 treatment. (E) Representative Western blot of
1378 total lysates of HEK 293FT cells transfected with *SALLI*²⁷⁵-YFP (lanes 1 and 3) or
1379 YFP alone (lanes 2 and 4) treated (+) or not (-) with MG132. Specific antibodies
1380 against LUZP1, GFP and GAPDH were used. One black arrowhead indicates
1381 *SALLI*²⁷⁵-YFP, two back arrowheads YFP alone. (F) Graphical representation of the
1382 fold changes of LUZP1/GAPDH ratios obtained in (E) for HEK 293FT cells
1383 transfected with *SALLI*²⁷⁵-YFP (orange dots) or YFP alone (blue dots) treated (+) or
1384 not (-) with MG132. Note that LUZP1 increases in the presence of MG132 when
1385 *SALLI*²⁷⁵-YFP was transfected. Data from at least three independent experiments
1386 pooled together are shown. *P*-values were calculated using two-tailed unpaired
1387 Student's t-test. (G) Immunofluorescence micrographs of RPE1 cells treated
1388 (+MG132) or not (-MG132) with proteasome inhibitor showing LUZP1 associated
1389 with the cytoskeleton (upper panels) or in the centrosome (lower panels). Antibodies
1390 against endogenous LUZP1 (green), Centrin-2 (CETN2, blue) and CEP164 (magenta)
1391 were used. DAPI labelled the nuclei (blue). Single green channels are shown in black
1392 and white. Note the overall increase of LUZP1 upon MG132 treatment. Scale bar 10
1393 μm (cytoskeleton panels) or 0.5 μm (centrosome panels). Imaging was performed
1394 using widefield fluorescence microscopy (Zeiss Axioimager D1, 63x objective). (H)
1395 Western blot analysis of input and biotin pulldown (PD) of HEK 293FT cells

1396 transfected with *CMV-LUZP1-YFP* and BioUb or BirA alone treated (+) or not (-)
1397 with MG132. Specific antibodies (GFP, GAPDH, Biotin) were used as indicated.
1398 Numbers under GFP panel are the result of dividing each biotin PD band intensity by
1399 the respective input band intensity and normalize them to lane 1. Molecular weight
1400 markers in kDa are shown to the right. Two asterisks indicate monoubiquitinated
1401 LUZP1.

1402 The following figure supplement is available for Figure 9:

1403 Figure 9-figure supplement 1. Full western blot images for Figure 9.

1404 Figure 9-figure supplement 2. LUZP1 mRNA expression levels.

1405

1406 **Figure 10. LUZP1 overexpression suppresses ciliogenesis and increases F-actin**

1407 **levels.** (A) Representative micrographs of ciliated Control and TBS²⁷⁵ cells

1408 transduced with *YFP* or *LUZP1-YFP* expressing lentivirus. Yellow arrowhead and

1409 white asterisk point at a magnified region shown in the lower right panel in black and

1410 white. Note the lack of cilia in cells transduced with LUZP1-YFP (white asterisk)

1411 compared to non-transduced cells (yellow arrow). AcTub: acetylated alpha-tubulin

1412 (magenta); CETN2: Centrin-2 (blue). (B) Graphical representation of the number of

1413 ciliated cells per micrograph in Control and TBS²⁷⁵ cells overexpressing *YFP* or

1414 *LUZP1-YFP* (n>10 micrographs). Graphs represent Mean and SEM of ciliation

1415 frequencies per micrograph in three independent experiments pulled together. *P*-

1416 values were calculated using One-way ANOVA and Bonferroni post-hoc test or two-

1417 tailed unpaired Student's t-test. (C) Representative micrographs of Control and

1418 TBS²⁷⁵ cells transduced with *YFP* (yellow arrowhead) or *LUZP1-YFP* (white asterisk)

1419 co-stained with phalloidin to label F-actin (magenta) and DAPI (blue). Note the

1420 increase in F-actin levels in cells transduced with LUZP1-YFP (white asterisk)

1421 compared to non-transfected cells (yellow arrow). Scale bar, 10 μ m. Imaging was
1422 performed using widefield fluorescence microscopy (Zeiss Axioimager D1, 63x
1423 objective). **(D)** Schematic model representing how the presence of truncated SALL1
1424 might cause cilia and actin malformations in TBS through LUZP1 interaction and
1425 UPS-mediated degradation. In control (or fed) cells (left), LUZP1 (in green) localizes
1426 to F-actin and to the proximal ends of the two centrioles, inhibiting cilia formation.
1427 LUZP1 proteostasis is maintained by the Ubiquitin Proteasome System (UPS). By
1428 contrast, in TBS (or starved) cells (right) the truncated form of SALL1 interacts with
1429 LUZP1 and promotes its UPS-mediated degradation. Likewise, others have shown
1430 ubiquitination and proteasome-mediated degradation of CCP110 at the mother
1431 centriole (MC) is permissive for ciliogenesis (Li et al., 2013). LUZP1 reduction at the
1432 centrosome and at the cytoskeleton favors the formation of the primary cilia.

1433 The following figure supplement is available for Figure 10:

1434 Figure 10-figure supplement 1. Exogenous LUZP1 expression suppresses the positive
1435 effects of CytoD on ciliogenesis.

1436

1437

1438 **FIGURE SUPPLEMENT LEGENDS**

1439 **Figure 1-figure supplement 1. Full western blot images for Figure 1.** Title
1440 indicates the Figure to which the Western blot corresponds; magenta boxes show the
1441 region of the gel that was used to build the indicated figures. SALL1^{FL} protein is
1442 indicated by one asterisk, SALL1 truncated forms by one black arrowhead, YFP alone
1443 by two black arrowheads. One empty arrowhead indicate truncated forms, bands from
1444 previous probing or unspecific bands. Molecular weight markers are shown to the
1445 right.

1446

1447 **Figure 1-figure supplement 2. Analysis of TbID constructs expression and**

1448 **biotinylation localization.** (A) Western blot of inputs or GFP-Trap pulldowns

1449 performed in HEK 293FT cells transfected with *SALLI*²⁷⁵-YFP (lanes 1 and 6),

1450 *SALLI*^{FL}-YFP (lanes 2 and 7), YFP alone (lanes 3 and 8), *SALLI*²⁷⁵-YFP together with

1451 *SALLI*^{FL}-2xHA (*SALLI*^{FL}-HA; lanes 4 and 9) or *SALLI*^{FL}-HA together with YFP

1452 alone (lanes 5 and 10). Specific antibodies (LUZP1, actin, SALL1) were used as

1453 indicated. Numbers under LUZP1 panel result from dividing band intensities of each

1454 pulldown by their respective input levels. One asterisk indicates BirA*-*SALLI*^{FL} or

1455 *SALLI*^{FL}-YFP, one black arrowhead *SALLI*²⁷⁵-YFP and two black arrowheads YFP

1456 alone. Molecular weight markers (kDa) are shown to the right. Actin was used as

1457 loading control. Blots shown are representative of three independent experiments. (B)

1458 Western blot analysis of RPE1 cells transfected with TbID-LUZP1 or TbID alone.

1459 Specific antibodies (BirA, LUZP1 and GAPDH) were used as indicated. Anti-BirA

1460 antibody detected the fusion form of TbID-LUZP1 (two asterisks) or TbID (three

1461 asterisks). LUZP1 antibodies detected endogenous LUZP1 (two empty arrowheads)

1462 and TbID-LUZP1 (two arrowheads). Molecular weight markers are shown to the right.

1463 (C) In RPE1 cells transfected with TbID-LUZP1, streptavidin (green) localizes to the

1464 centrosome labelled with Pericentrin (PCNT, magenta) or actin fibers labelled with

1465 phalloidin (Phall, magenta). No biotinylation in microtubules, labelled by β Tubulin

1466 (β Tub, magenta), was observed. By contrast, cells transfected with TbID show

1467 streptavidin labeling in nucleus and cytoplasm. Green channels are shown in black

1468 and white. Arrowheads indicate the centrioles. Note that basal actin stress fibers are

1469 less evident when apical centrioles are in focus.

1470

1471 **Figure 2-figure supplement 1. Centrosomal localization of LUZP1 at different**
1472 **cell cycle stages.** Immunofluorescence micrographs showing LUZP1 in the
1473 centrosome during cell cycle in RPE1 cells. Cells were treated with mimosine (G1
1474 phase), thymidine (S phase), RO-3306 (G2/M phase) or starved (G0) with and
1475 without the proteasome inhibitor MG132. Cells were stained in green with antibodies
1476 against endogenous LUZP1, and in blue with DAPI. Scale bar 0.5 μ m. Imaging was
1477 performed using widefield fluorescence microscopy (Zeiss Axioimager D1, 63x
1478 objective). On the lower right panel, graphical representation of the percentage of
1479 cells showing the presence of LUZP1 at the centrosome per micrograph,
1480 corresponding to the experiment in (A); $n > 6$ micrographs. Note a general decrease of
1481 LUZP1 during G2/M and upon starvation (G0), which is recovered by MG132
1482 addition. Graphs represent Mean and SEM of three independent experiments pooled
1483 together. *P*-values were calculated using Kruskal-Wallis and Dunn's multiple
1484 comparisons test. ** over G2/M and G0 columns indicate that they are significantly
1485 different from the rest of the columns and not significant amongst them.

1486

1487 **Figure 3-figure supplement 1. Full western blot images for Figure 3.** Title
1488 indicates the Figure to which the Western blot corresponds; magenta boxes show the
1489 region of the gel that was used to build the indicated figures. LUZP1-YFP is indicated
1490 by two empty arrowheads and GFP or YFP alone by two black arrowheads. One
1491 empty arrowhead indicate truncated forms, bands from previous probing or unspecific
1492 bands. Molecular weight markers are shown to the right.

1493

1494 **Figure 4-figure supplement 1. Full western blot images for Figure 4.** Titles
1495 indicate the Figure to which the Western blot corresponds; magenta boxes show the

1496 region of the gel that was used to build the indicated figures. LUZP1-YFP is indicated
1497 by two empty arrowheads and YFP alone by two black arrowheads. Bands from
1498 previous probing or unspecific bands are indicated by one empty arrowhead.
1499 Molecular weight markers are shown to the right.

1500

1501 **Figure 5-figure supplement 1. Full western blot images for Figure 5.** Title
1502 indicates the Figure to which the Western blot corresponds; magenta boxes show the
1503 region of the gel that was used to build the indicated figures. Molecular weight
1504 markers are shown to the right.

1505

1506 **Figure 7-figure supplement 1. Full western blot images for Figure 7.** Title
1507 indicates the Figure to which the Western blot corresponds; magenta boxes show the
1508 region of the gel that was used to build the indicated figures. Molecular weight
1509 markers are shown to the right.

1510

1511 **Figure 9-figure supplement 1. Full western blot images for Figure 9.** Titles
1512 indicate the Figure to which the Western blot corresponds; magenta boxes show the
1513 region of the gel that was used to build the indicated figures. Ubiquitinated LUZP1 is
1514 indicated by two asterisks, LUZP1-YFP by two empty arrowheads and YFP alone by
1515 two black arrowheads. One empty arrowhead indicate truncated forms, bands from
1516 previous probing or unspecific bands. Molecular weight markers are shown to the
1517 right.

1518

1519 **Figure 9-figure supplement 2. LUZP1 mRNA expression levels.** Quantification of
1520 *LUZP1* expression in control (ESCTRL2) vs TBS²⁷⁵ cells by qRT-PCR. Graphs

1521 represent Mean and SEM from 5 independent experiments. P-values were calculated
1522 using the Mann Whitney test.

1523

1524 **Figure 10-figure supplement 1. Exogenous LUZP1 expression suppresses the**
1525 **positive effects of CytoD on ciliogenesis.** (A) Representative micrographs of ciliated
1526 RPE1 cells transduced with *YFP* or *LUZP1-YFP* treated with DMSO (-) or 50 nM
1527 CytoD for 16 hours (+). Yellow arrowhead point to cilia. Note the lack of cilia in cells
1528 transduced with *LUZP1-YFP* (white asterisk) compared to non-transduced cells.
1529 ARL13B labelled the cilia (magenta) and Centrin-2 the centrosomes (CETN2, blue).
1530 Scale bars indicate 10 μ m. (B) Graphical representation of the number of ciliated cells
1531 per micrograph in RPE1 cells transduced with *YFP* or *LUZP1-YFP* (n>10
1532 micrographs). Graphs represent Mean and SEM of ciliation frequencies per
1533 micrograph in three independent experiments pulled together. P-values were
1534 calculated using two-tailed unpaired Student's t-test.

1535

1536 **RICH DATA**

1537 **Figure 2-video 1. LUZP1 localization in the centrosome.** 3D reconstruction of Z-
1538 stack micrographs of human control fibroblasts (ESCTRL#2) stained with antibodies
1539 against endogenous LUZP1 (green) and acetylated alpha and gamma tubulin to label
1540 the cilia and centrosomes, respectively (magenta). Image was taken using Confocal
1541 Super-resolution microscopy (LSM 980, Zeiss).

1542

1543 **SOURCE DATA**

1544 **Source Data 1. Identification of LUZP1 interactors by proximity proteomics.**

1545 **Source Data 2. Values used for graphical representations and statistical analysis.**

1546

1547

A

Figure 1A

Figure 1-figure supplement 2A

Figure 1-figure supplement 2A

Figure 1-figure supplement 2B

Figure 3D

Figure 3D

Figure 3E

Figure 3F

Figure 4D

Figure 4E

Figure 5C

Figure 7C

Figure 9A

Figure 9C

Figure 9E

Figure 9H

Figure 9H

**LUZP1 mRNA expression
(fold change)**

A